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Local Italian Alimurgical Species

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The large variety of alimurgical species

Alimurgy, from the Latin “*alimentia urgentia*”, refers to the nutritional opportunity offered by a number of wild plant species. About 10% of the world flora is known as edible. This would correspond to roughly 50,000 species. Just in Italy, a biodiversity hotspot amid the Mediterranean basin, more than 800 species are recognised edible. Whatever the exact numbers, many alimurgical species are known and used just at the local level, thus representing a reservoir of opportunities for the development of local economies. Especially, the harvest of wild species provides occasions in the eco-touristic and gastronomic fields. Multipurpose farms, furnishing hospitality and catering to their clients, might gain a significant income by adding value to the alimurgical products. In fact, proposing meals based on spontaneous products of the territory represents a gastronomic way to engage the guests in the local culture, thus providing added value to the spontaneous edible species. Most often, aside the peculiar taste of each alimurgical species and the attractive sensorial experience, wild species are rich in nutraceutical compounds owing to their rusticity and adaptability to local environments. Other than their mineral contents, which have important nutritional value, the spontaneous species are often rich in vitamins, polyphenols and other antioxidant molecules. This increases their reputation among the consumers, spreading a sense of healthiness linked to their alimentary use. The most common and renowned Italian species that yield a significant added value on the local catering are just a few. The wild chicory (*Cichorium intybus* L.) pays the higher price in terms of consumption. However, many other wild species are currently harvested and, in some cases, cultivated: *Borrago officinalis* L., *Urtica dioica* L., *Plantago major* L. and *P. lanceolata* L., *Taraxacum officinalis* L., *Portulaca oleracea* L., just to list a few.

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